

Design and Development of New Chemical Reactions via Low-valent Titanium-induced Cleavage of Carbon - Heteroatom Bonds

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Low-valent titanium (LVT)-induced regioselective cleavage of *N*-arylmethyl bonds in preference to *N*-alkyl/aryl counterparts in *N*-arylmethylamines has been examined in detail and culminated in the design and development of new reactions, viz. novel approach to deprotection of *N*-benzylamines, reductive deoxygenation of carbonyls to methylenes and reductive amination of carbonyls under neutral conditions—all involving a known bonding change, viz. the directed cleavage of C–N bonds via LVT-mediated reactions.

The invention of chemical reactions is a challenging and rewarding undertaking¹. Although several important chemical processes such as the Birch reduction, the Wittig reaction or Brown's hydroboration were invented by chance or by accident, there is considerable scope for the rational design of chemical reactions. Developments of new chemical reactions continue to be in focus of research activity in organic chemistry. Essentially chemical reactions involve change in bondings. Selective bond formation or cleavage is therefore the essence for the development of new chemical reactions leading to the formation of complex molecular architecture¹. Hence cleavage of carbon-heteroatom bonds is an important subject in contemporary synthetic organic chemistry.

Organometallic chemistry has made a major impact in the design of novel synthetic strategies. The emergence of transition metal mediated organic reactions^{2a,b} at the frontiers of organic synthesis has provided new *chemo*-, *regio*-, and *stereoselective* transformations. Use of LVT reagents^{3a-d} are however of recent origin and are finding increasing applications in diversified organic synthesis. LVT-based reagents combine a high reducing ability with pronounced oxophilicity and act as one-electron reductants in organic transformations. The present article discloses the recent applications of LVT reagents from our laboratory towards the single electron transfer (SET) induced cleavage of carbon-heteroatom bonds and their consequences to the rational design and development of new chemical reactions.

LVT-mediated SET-induced cleavage of carbon-nitrogen bond—the key reaction

A LVT-mediated SET-induced novel approach to selective deprotection of *O*-allyl-, *O*-benzyl- and *O*-propargyl ethers of alcohols and phenols was reported from this laboratory earlier^{4a,b}. The preferential cleavage of *O*-allyl/benzyl/propargyl bonds over *O*-methyl group could be attributed to the differential stability of the respective intermedi-

ate η -complexes with titanium. Based on these findings, it could be argued that *N*-benzyl/allyl bonds should also undergo cleavages through SET mechanism though at comparatively slower rates. The higher oxophilicity of LVT species than their affinity for nitrogen coupled with lower electronegativity of nitrogen compared to oxygen is expected to render the carbon-nitrogen (C–N) bond in *N*-allyl/benzylamines less susceptible to attack than their oxygen counterparts. In order to verify this hypothesis, a systematic study on the effects of LVT on the cleavage of C–N bonds in amines having different chemical environments was undertaken.

Directed cleavage of C–N bonds in amines

The C–N bonds in *N*-trialkyl/aryl amines are resistant to cleavage towards LVT reagents. However, replacement of one alkyl/aryl group by arylmethyl functionality makes this particular C–N bond more prone to cleavage than the *N*-alkyl/aryl bonds. This is due to the formation of radical anion intermediate as a result of SET from LVT species to *N*-arylmethylamine derivative which in turn triggers *regioselective* homolytic cleavage of *N*-arylmethyl bond (Scheme 1). The driving force for the selective cleavage of *N*-arylmethyl bonds over the *N*-alkyl/aryl counterparts could be due to formation of resonance stabilized arylmethyl radical compared to alkyl/aryl radicals. The arylmethyl radical is quenched ultimately by hydrogen (from solvent) to arylalkane (II).

Scheme 1

Thus the key reaction involves the *regioselective* C–N bond cleavage in *N*-arylmethylamines leading to two components, viz. the free debenzylated amine (amine part, I) when Ar = Ph, and the arylalkane (non-amine part, II)

(Scheme 1). This reaction at the first sight offers a new protocol for the deprotection of *N*-benzylamines in a very straight forward manner. However, the hidden and enriched chemical information comprising this bonding change can be further unfolded for the development of new and novel chemical processes. Thus this one reaction has been judiciously utilized towards the development of new reactions in addition to deprotection of *N*-benzylamines, e.g. deoxygenation and reductive amination of carbonyls. The underlying concepts and the logic which have provided additional opportunities to new chemical processes involving the directed C–N bond cleavage in amines are presented in Scheme 2. For reductive amination or deoxygenation to perform, the carbonyl compounds are first converted to the desired amine derivatives (III) via intermediacy of imine. By judicious selection of the substituents, preferential cleavage of C–N bond on either side of III can be directed. Hence cleavage through path 'a' leads to reductive amination and on the other hand, reaction through path 'b' results reductive deoxygenation — thus offering two important functional group transformations involving carbonyl group.

Deprotection of *N*-benzylamines

The skilful selection, introduction, and removal of protective groups^{5,6} play a major role in organic syntheses including total syntheses of natural products. Protection of amino function⁶ is called for in the synthesis of many compounds and particularly in peptides. Several groups have been developed for the protection of amino functionality. However, amongst different protective groups, *N*-benzylamine and *N*-allylamine are more frequently used. The success of any protective group largely depends upon its stability to acidic and non-acidic reagents, ease of installation, and removal. Most of debenzylamine processes⁶, in-

cluding the *O*-benzyl group involve a Lewis acid-catalyzed reaction or the reduction with sodium in liquid ammonia or catalytic hydrogenation. Thus, the discovery of neutral reagents for deprotection is highly warranted. The present work throws light in this direction wherein a SET-induced strategy for the deprotection of *N*-allyl/benzylamines has been formulated using LVT reagents under neutral condition.

In a model experiment, reaction was carried out by refluxing a mixture of *N*-allyldiphenylamine (1b) and LVT (generated *in situ* from TiCl₃-Li-THF). The progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc. Reaction was complete after 20 h. Working up of the reaction mixture afforded diphenylamine (2b) in 65% yield (Table 1, entry 1). Compared to *O*-deallylation which was much faster (2.5 h)^{4a}, *N*-deallylation required more time to complete, as predicted.

TABLE 1—CLEAVAGE OF *N*-ALLYL- AND *N*-BENZYLAMINES WITH LVT

Entry no.	Substrate	Conditions reflux time, h	Product(s)	Yield %
1.	1b	20	2b	65
2.	1c	20	2c	47
3.	3b	22	4b 4'b	49 47
4.	3c	22	4c(=4b) 4'c	47 47
5.	1a	18	2a	48
6.	3a	22	2a	55
7.	1d	18	2d	49
8.	5a	16	6a	48
9.	7a	5	8a 8b	53 42

Scheme 2

The scope of this methodology has been illustrated by the deprotection of a variety of *N*-allyl/benzylamines (Scheme 3). The reaction is quite general for *N*-benzyl and allyl derivatives of amines of aliphatic, aromatic as well as alicyclic origin. As an example of alicyclic compounds, deallylation of *N*-allyldicyclohexylamine (1c) (Table 1, entry 2) was carried out successfully. This protocol could be used for substituted benzylamines also. Thus, in the cases of *N*-(4-*N,N*-dimethylaminobenzyl)aniline (3b) (Table 1, entry 3) and *N*-(2-hydroxybenzyl)aniline (3c) (Table 2, entry 4), aniline (4b) was obtained in both the cases. Hence, in addition to simple benzyl protection, substituted benzyl groups can also be used for the protection of amines.

under these conditions is evidenced from the formation of *N*-methylaniline (2a) from *N*-methyl-*N*-allylaniline (1a) (Table 1, entry 5). Similarly, *regioselective N*-debenzylation could be carried out in the presence of *N*-Me group. Thus, when *N*-benzyl-*N*-methylaniline (3a) and *N*-(4-*N,N*-dimethylaminobenzyl)aniline (3b) were treated with LVT, *N*-methylaniline (2a) (Table 1, entry 6) and aniline (4b) (Table 1, entry 3) were obtained respectively. *Regioselective* cleavage of allyl group could be shown by using substrates containing both *N*-allyl and *N*-benzyl groups. Thus, *N*-allyl-*N*-benzylaniline (1d) furnished *N*-benzylaniline (2d) (Table 1, entry 7) as a result of preferential cleavage of *N*-allyl bond. *Chemoselective* cleavage of *O*-benzyl bond could

Scheme 3

Regio- and chemoselectivity

The selective monoprotection of a given function in a heterofunctional molecule constitutes a challenging task in organic synthesis. In the present study, both *regio*- and *chemoselectivities* are maintained thereby offering efficient protocol for amine deprotection. Both *N*-benzyl and *N*-allyl bonds cleave in a *regioselective* manner in presence of *N*-methyl group. That the *N*-CH₃ group remains unaffected

be achieved in preference to *N*-benzyl bond thus allowing selective protection (debenzylation) in amino-alcohols. Thus, 2-hydroxybenzylaniline (6a) was obtained as the sole product when 2-benzyloxy-*N*-benzylaniline (5a) was used as substrate (Table 1, entry 8).

As stated above, the preferential cleavage of *N*-benzyl bond over *N*-methyl group is possibly due to the stability gained through resonance in benzyl radical after cleavage.

Use of cinnamyl group is expected to impart more stability to the radical thereby enhancing the lability of the C–N bond cleavage. Thus compared to benzyl group, cinnamyl moiety could be a better protecting group. Indeed, *N*-cinnamyl group was cleaved at a faster rate and required only 5 h compared to *N*-benzyl group (Table 1, entry 9). 2-Methoxyaniline (**8a**) was obtained from *N*-cinnamyl-2-methoxyaniline (**7a**). The cinnamyl group therefore holds considerable promise as a new protective group for amines. This reaction also shows the compatibility of methoxy groups under the present reaction condition.

Thus the SET-induced LVT-mediated protocol^{7a} for the deprotection of *N*-benzyl or *N*-allyl amines holds promise in both aliphatic and aromatic domain. *Regio*- and *chemoselectivities* are maintained. *N*-Methyl or *O*-methyl group remains unaffected under the reaction conditions. *N*-Cinnamyl group is cleaved at a faster rate compared to its benzyl counterpart. This along with our earlier reports^{4a,b} offer several protocols for the protection of alcohols, phenols and amines in multistep syntheses of many bioactive compounds.

Reductive deoxygenation of carbonyls to methylenes

As described above, during the deprotection of *N*-benzyl derivatives of amines, the attention was focused towards the regeneration^{7a} of the amine (**I**) (Scheme 1). It was postulated that during the cleavage of *N*-arylmethyl bonds with LVT, the stable arylmethyl radical is quenched by hydrogen from the solvent (THF). This hypothesis was supported by the actual isolation of arylmethanes in some of the cases. The propensity of LVT to selectively cleave the *N*-arylmethyl bonds to the corresponding free amine and alkane has now been utilized for the development of yet another useful synthetic protocol, viz. deoxygenation of aryl carbonyls to the corresponding methylenes. Here the emphasis was given to the arylmethyl part, i.e. the non-amine part (**II**) of the *N*-arylmethyl derivatives of amines (Scheme 1). Thus this section presents invention of new chemical reactions utilizing the known bonding change involving the C–N bonds.

The conversion of carbonyl functions in aldehydes and ketones to methylene groups is a synthetically useful reaction and various methods⁸ have been developed for this transformation. Clemmensen reduction (C.R.) has long been known to convert a carbonyl function to the corresponding methylene group in strongly acidic conditions. This method cannot be used for acid-labile compounds, but is complemented by Wolf-Kishner reduction (W.K.R.) and related reactions which are carried out under basic media. However, W.K.R. is hampered by steric hindrance surrounding the carbonyl group primarily due to the difficulty in the requisite hydrazone formation.

Mixed hydride reagents such as LAH or NaBH₄ in com-

TABLE 2—DEOXYGENATION OF CARBONYLS TO METHYLENES

Entry no	Compd. no.	Ar	R	Time ^b h	Yield ^a of 11(%)
1.	9a, 10a, 11a	2-HO-C ₆ H ₄	H	22	48
2	9b, 10b, 11b	4-HO-C ₆ H ₄	H	22	46
3	9c, 10c, 11c	4-Me ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	H	20	49
4	9d, 10d, 11d	3-Indolyl	H	22	47
5.	9e, 10e, 11e	Ph	Ph	22	48
6.	9f, 10f, 11f	2-Naph	Me	18	48
7.	9g, 10g, 11g	2-(1-HO-Naph)	Et	20	55
8.	9h, 10h, 11h	Ph	(CH ₂) ₂ CO ₂ H	16	67
9.	9i, 10i	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	H	22	57 ^c
10	9j, 10j	4-MeO-C ₆ H ₄	H	19	48 ^c

^aYields are based on intermediate *N*-(arylmethyl)anilines (**10**), conversions for **9** → **10** are above 90% in all the cases. ^bReactions for **10** → **11** conversions performed under reflux. ^cPhCH₂NHPh is the sole product isolated.

ination with Lewis acids are widely applicable but lack selectivity. Catalytic hydrogenolysis, diborane, lithium in ammonia, and organosilicon hydrides are mild reducing agents but are incompatible with compounds having double or triple bonds. There are also other reagents, viz. mixture of HI and red phosphorous which are not generally applicable. Indirect methods such as the reduction of tosylhydrazones of aldehydes and ketones and the desulfurization of thioacetals are in general mild and selective. However, these methods involve multistep sequences and the yields are variable.

Thus, the formation of side-products due to unusual reductions, interferences due to steric consequences, and drastic conditions used in these reactions limit their synthetic utility for sensitive polyfunctional compounds. Although, several subsequent modifications and alternatives have alleviated⁸ some of the problems, there is still need for the development of selective and better strategies for deoxygenation of carbonyl compounds. Herein, a protocol for selective conversion of aryl carbonyls to the corresponding methylenes via the intermediacy of *N*-(arylmethyl)anilines using LVT reagent is presented which essentially involves C–N bond cleavage. This methodology, in principle, provides an indirect strategy for oxygen removal from carbonyls under neutral condition.

The protocol consists of conversion of aldehydes or ketones (**9**) to the Schiff's bases by condensation with aniline. Subsequently, the Schiff's bases are reduced with NaBH₄ to the *N*-(arylmethyl)anilines (**10**) in one-pot (Scheme 4). Choice of aniline as a condensing base was made because of its inexpensiveness, easy availability, and facile reactivity towards aryl carbonyls. Treatment of *N*-(arylmethyl)anilines (**10**) with LVT (generated *in situ* from TiCl₃-Li-THF) brings about *regioselective* cleavage of *N*-

arylmethyl bond generating aniline and the corresponding alkanes (11). Thus, in effect, this procedure offers a synthetically useful method for the conversion of carbonyls to methylenes through the initial activation of carbonyls by derivatisation to *N*-(arylmethyl)anilines via intermediacy of Schiff's bases.

Ar = aryl; R = H, alkyl, aryl

Scheme 4

Generality, selectivity and utility

To explore the scope of the protocol, experiments have been carried out using a variety of carbonyl compounds. Table 2 presents several examples which illustrate the utility and selectivity of the transformation. The protocol is applicable to aryl aldehydes (entries 1-4), as well as diaryl and arylalkyl ketones (entries 5-8). The deoxygenation can easily be performed *chemoselectively* in the presence of reducible alkyl acid functionality (entry 8), arylhydroxyl (entries 1, 2 and 7) and arylamino (entry 3) functionalities. Steric factor is of less significance for the cleavage of *N*-benzyl bond. Thus, relative increase in steric bulk surrounding the carbonyl in ketones such as 2-naphthyl methyl ketone (entry 6) and 2-(1-hydroxynaphthyl)ethyl ketone (entry 7) does not hamper their conversions to the corresponding alkanes. Thus this protocol offers an advantage over the existing W.K.R. or C.R. which fails in sterically crowded environments. The methodology has been extended to nitrogen heterocycles such as indole system which forms the basic unit in numerous natural products. Thus, 3-formylindole (entry 4) could be successfully converted to skatole providing access to important C-alkylindoles^{7b}. This protocol of deoxygenation has the limitation in cases of chlorinated or methoxylated aryl carbonyls. Thus, both *N*-(4-chlorobenzyl)aniline (entry 9) and *N*-(4-methoxybenzyl)aniline (entry 10) derived from *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde and *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde respectively, yielded *N*-benzylaniline as the sole product resulting from preferential dechlorination or demethoxylation over *N*-benzyl bond cleavage.

Thus a new LVT-mediated transformation⁹ of aryl carbonyls to the corresponding methylenes has been formulated. It provides a mild, convenient and selective pathway for deoxygenation of carbonyls without the production of any side-product. In contrast to Clemmensen (acidic) and Wolff-Kishner (basic) methods, the simplicity and neutral reaction conditions of this methodology will find wider applications. This method of deoxygenation is applicable to

both aryl aldehydes and ketones. Hindered carbonyls could be reliably reduced to hydrocarbons without any side-reactions. Easy access to the starting materials allows for a broad applicability. However, this protocol is not applicable to aryl carbonyls containing reducible halide or methoxyl groups wherein facile cleavage of halogen or methoxyl functionalities takes place in preference to *N*-benzyl bond cleavage.

Reductive amination of carbonyls (*trans*-amination)

The involvement of amino functionality in a multitude of biological activities is well-documented. Strategies which allow the access of this unit is particularly important from the standpoint of bioorganic chemistry. The generation of amino groups in concert with the functionalized carbon framework is particularly important for the synthesis of ligands for metal-based radiopharmaceuticals^{10a-c} and is the cornerstone of bioorganometallics. Reductive amination⁸ of carbonyls offers attractive possibilities for the direct access to a plethora of amines. In fact, this constitutes the most useful reaction in the synthesis of primary, secondary, and tertiary amines. The Birch reduction⁸ using sodium cyanoborohydride (NaBH₃CN) has been the most popular method to carry out this transformation. However, the toxicity of the reagent due to the risk associated with the residual cyanide in the product or in the work-up waste system poses serious environmental hazards. In addition, the commercially available reagent suffers from severe limitations due to their low solubility in common solvents. Herein we describe a conceptually different approach to reductive amination of carbonyls, based on the LVT-mediated SET-induced C-N bond cleavage in *N*-benzylamine derivatives.

Focal theme of the concept

The advantage of the *regioselective* C-N bond cleavage described earlier has been utilized for the present transformation. The protocol consists in the conversion of aliphatic carbonyls (12) to the corresponding Schiff's bases by reacting with benzylamine. The subsequent reduction of the imine with NaBH₄ produces the required amine derivative (13) containing both *N*-benzyl and *N*-alkyl moieties (Scheme 5). The resultant amine (13) undergoes *regioselective* cleavage of *N*-benzyl bond, thus transferring the amine fragment to the carbonyl residue (14). The protocol however is restricted to aliphatic carbonyls so that there is only one mode

Scheme 5

of cleavage of C–N bond. The introduced *N*-benzyl bond directs the *regioselective* C–N bond cleavage which ultimately guarantees the desired *trans*-amination.

The present protocol of reductive amination is restricted to aliphatic carbonyls. This therefore holds considerable promise in the synthesis of aminosugars which are fundamental constituents of glycolipids and glycoproteins and are involved in a variety of biochemical processes. This reaction can be adopted for the preparation of chiral amines too either by the conversion of the prochiral ketone to the prochiral imine followed by reduction using a chiral catalyst or reagent, or by formation of chiral imine of the prochiral ketone using a chiral benzylamine. In addition, the amine transfer from benzyl moiety to the carbonyl residue holds promise towards the synthesis of radiolabelled amines using isotopically (*N*)-labeled benzylamines.

Thus a convenient, environmentally safe protocol for reductive amination using state-of-the-art methodologies for *N*-benzyl bond cleavage has been developed which is likely to augment the accessibility to a variety of amines through easier pathway.

Conclusion

This article, therefore, highlights that any bond cleaving reaction is a store-house of plethora of relevant chemical information which requires rational cultivation, proper diagnosis, and rigorous retrosynthetic analysis for the design and development of new chemical reactions. The basic and the key reaction can therefore be exploited and directed for the invention of new chemical reactions. Thus the propensity of the C–N bond cleavage in *N*-benzylamines has been shown to have considerable potential to synthetic organic chemists in various directions opening up additional possibilities for new chemical transformations. Hence a comprehensive study on *N*-benzyl bond cleavage has culminated in the strategical design and development of new reactions, viz. novel approach to debenylation of amines, reductive deoxygenation of carbonyls to methylenes, and

reductive amination of carbonyls, all involving a known bonding change.

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